

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation
in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Quality Plan

Deliverable 8.1

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Description
AB	Multi-Actor Advisory Board
AFM	Administrative and Financial Manager
CR	Control Report
EC	Executive Committee
QB	Quality Board
RP	Reporting period
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Participant acronym	Description
UAntwerp	University of Antwerp
CMCC	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change
ACTERRA	Acterra
E3M	E3-Modelling
PIK	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
VERHAERT	Verhaert
FEUGA	Fundación Empresa-Universidad Gallega
NCSR	National Center for Scientific Research “Demokritos”
CZU	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague
LUT	LUT University
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
UVIGO	University of Vigo
EPSILON	EPSILON
ADEME	ADEME Guadeloupe
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust
MEDSEA	Mediterranean Sea and Coast Foundation
CETMAR	Fundación CETMAR: Centro Tecnológico del Mar
LAPP	Lappeenranta Municipality
MOE	Egaleo Municipality
WE	Water Europe
EQY	Euroquality
MOG	Municipality of Gjøvik

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TransformAr – Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation packages – is an H2020 project funded under the H2020 Programme, coordinated by the University of Antwerp.

The TransformAr project, launched on October 1st 2021, aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The project, funded by the EU Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement No 101036683, gathers 22 partnering organisations from 11 Member States. It has an overall budget of approximately €12 million and will run for 4 years, between October 2021 and September 2025.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Quality Plan defines, in accordance with the definitions and regulations of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the proper implementation of the general working mechanisms and information flow of the project, while defining quality policies and plans to be applied in the lifetime of the TransformAr project. The aim of this document is to provide guidelines and principles that ensure a high technical and managerial quality of the TransformAr project from start to completion. The present document is to be considered as an applicable document up to the final acceptance of all deliverables and reports. Any changes will be agreed upon by the Project Coordinator and the Executive Committee, and be included in a revised version of the present document. This document is also complemented by Deliverable D8.2 - Project Management Plan. Complying with the Quality Plan falls under the responsibility of the Project Coordinator, the Executive Committee - including Work Package Leaders - and the Task Leaders.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 TransformAr Quality Plan Objectives

The TransformAr Quality Plan intends to clarify quality assurance procedures for TransformAr, while ensuring that all project output, including deliverables, are of high quality and submitted to the European Commission in a timely manner. This deliverable also aims to ensure a high-quality standard for management processes and risk management procedures. Quality assurance procedures that are incorporated in these aims include mechanisms for the submission of deliverables and reports, the internal review process of TransformAr project partners and the correct use of project templates. The Quality Plan further defines the structure of management and managerial procedures, roles and responsibilities of partners within the consortium, the decision-making process, the organisation of meetings, internal as well as external communication, and how to deal with confidential information and conflict management. In order to guarantee the relevance of the Quality Plan throughout the lifetime of TransformAr, it will be revisited and updated accordingly.

More precisely, the Quality Plan aims at depicting the following aspects:

- Project management overview
 - Project management structure
 - Governance of TransformAr: the Executive Committee
 - The Steering Committee
 - Multi-Actor Advisory Board
 - Quality Board
- Quality management
 - Quality assurance of deliverables
 - Roles and responsibilities
 - Deliverable review process
 - Quality criteria for deliverables
 - Quality assurance of other output
 - Technical quality assurance
 - TransformAr naming convention
- Project reporting
 - Internal Communication
 - External Communication
 - Cost monitoring
 - Official reporting
- Risk management
 - Risk analysis and mitigation measures
 - Conflict resolution

2.0 Project Management

2.1 Project management

Jan Cools, the **Project Coordinator (PC)** from the University of Antwerp, takes the overall responsibility of the project. He will coordinate the relations between the European Commission and the Steering Committee and will be responsible for transmitting the contractual documentation to the European Commission and to the partners.

The Project Coordinator is responsible, among other aspects, for:

- monitoring compliance by the consortium members with their obligations
- collecting and reviewing deliverables and reports (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority
- keeping the address list of consortium members and other contact persons updated and available
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other consortium members concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority
- providing, upon request, the consortium members with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the consortium members to present claims

An exhaustive list of all responsibilities of the PC are presented in detail in the TransformAr Consortium Agreement, to which all beneficiaries have agreed and will adhere.

The PC is supported by the project's **Technical Manager**, Amalie Bjornavold from the University of Antwerp, and by the **Administrative and Financial Manager**, Charlotte François from Euroquality. The latter is responsible in particular for supporting the Project Coordinator in the project implementation and the administrative and financial follow-up of the project. The TransformAr project management structure is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 TransformAr management structure

2.2 Governance of TransformAr: the Executive Committee

The **Executive Committee** (EC) is the body that ensures effective decision-making at both strategic and operational levels, while overseeing regular project management activities on a day-to-day basis. The EC is composed of each Work Package Leader, the Project Coordinator (PC) and the Technical Manager and the Administrative and Financial Manager. Minutes and decisions made during EC meetings are available to all partners on the project’s Microsoft Teams repository accessible to all consortium members.

The role of the EC is to report on advancements of the project and make structured decisions when needed. The EC holds monthly meetings to discuss these points, and specifically : (a) management and monitoring of project development according to the work plan; (b) guidance of the project with respect to external development and potential collaborations; (c) review of the general scientific and technical program and of the project outcomes; (d) monitoring of the quality management plan as well as review and approval of the risk assessment; (e) conflict resolution management; and (f) review and approval of financial issues.

Each **Work Package Leader** (WPL, detailed in Table 1) is responsible for the coordination of the work of the partners collaborating on that work package. They will be in direct and frequent contact with task leaders and the Project Coordinator, and will make sure that deliverables are completed, while meeting the appropriate quality standards on time.

Table 1 TransformAr Work Package Leaders

Work Package	WPL	WPL representant
WP1. Innovation ecosystems for transformational adaptation in demonstrators	FEUGA	Nuria Rodríguez-Aubó
WP2. Integrated biophysical/socio-economic framework for modelling multi-sector dynamics	CMCC	Antonio Trabucco
WP3. Envisioning transformative pathways for the demonstrators	ACTERRA	Rim Khamis
WP4. Actionable adaptive solutions implementation	ADEME	Marie-Edith Vincennes
WP5. Accelerating demonstrators’ transformational adaptation	WRT	Laurence Couldrick
WP6. Acceptance, building and exploitation of innovation packages	UA	Amalie Bjornavold
WP7. Structuring a EU transformational adaptation community of practice	WE	Ana De León
WP8. Project management	UA	Jan Cools

2.3 The Steering Committee

The **Steering Committee** is composed of representatives from each partner in the consortium. They will meet every six months during the project and are chaired by the Project Coordinator. The Steering Committee’s role is to supervise the overall progress of the project and is responsible for reviewing the technical and strategic aspects of the project. The project management team, in collaboration with the hosting partner is responsible for the organisation of the agenda of the meetings. A tentative schedule of Steering Committee in-person meetings is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Tentative schedule of TransformAr Steering Committee meetings

Time	Country and partner	Main items to be discussed	Back-to-back meeting
<i>October 2021 (M1)</i>	BE - UA	Overall objectives + Procedures and AF management	
<i>June 2022 (M9)</i>	IT- MEDSEA	Community building - Review by WP	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>November 2022 (M14)</i>	FR - ADEME	Risk assessment - Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>March 2023 (M18)</i>	ES - CETMAR	Pathway definition- Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>September 2023 (M24)</i>	FI - LAPP	Adaptive action plans/ portfolios - Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>March 2024 (M30)</i>	EL - MOE	Implementation of solutions - Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>September 2024 (M36)</i>	UK - WRT	Monitoring & accelerating - Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>March 2025 (M42)</i>	NO - MOG	Replication, exploitation - Review	One day of exchanges between demo
<i>September 2025 (M48)</i>	BE - UA	Achievements - Review by work package	

2.4 Multi-Actor Advisory Board

Considering the size and complexity of TransformAr, the consortium will be supported by a gender-balanced **Multi-Actor Advisory Board** (AB) that will deliver an external and critical review of its progress. The main profiles composing the AB will be experts from transformational adaptation and water at the international level, networks of territories and investors. Partners will identify new additional members for the Board in coming months.

TransformAr’s Multi-Actor Advisory Board’s role will be to facilitate the upscaling the project’s results and maximise its impacts. The AB will also provide direction and advice on the project development and will assist in dissemination. To achieve this, the Board members will make use of their own networks and are invited to the Steering Committee meetings every six months. The members of the Multi-Actor Advisory Board are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Multi-Actor Advisory Board

Name	Role
Linda Romanovska	Independent Expert member, EU Platform on Sustainable Finance Researcher, University of New South Wales
Andrija Erac	Sustainable Development Solutions Network-SDSN
Chris Dickens	International Water Management Institute – IWMI

2.5 Quality Board

Chaired by the Project Coordinator, the **Quality Board** (QB) will oversee quality control of major deliverables. The QB will be gender-balanced and composed of experts from cross-cutting topics that have been considered of crucial importance by the TransformAr consortium. The topics of gender, Responsible Research and Innovation, Exploitation and Open innovation, Data Management, Blue Growth, Environmental impact and Social Sciences and Humanities have been selected and will be considered in all project developments. For instance, the QB will provide a gender-marker guidelines and RRI analysis. Members of the QB are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 TransformAr Quality Board members

Topic	Member
Gender issues	Jérôme Oudart (EQY)
Exploitation and Open Innovation	Alfredo Varela Carrera (FEUGA)
Replication	Pål Godard (MOG)
Responsible Research and Innovation	Jan Cools (UA)
Data Management	Marc Bonazountas (EPSILON)
Blue Growth	Lucia Fraga (CETMAR)
Environmental Impact	Risto Soukka (LUT)
Social Sciences and Humanities	Chiara Trozzo (CMCC)

3.0 Quality management

3.1 Quality assurance of deliverables

In this section, the necessary activities to assess, analyse, and improve the quality of project outputs are described. The Project Coordinator must submit the deliverables in accordance with the timing and conditions set out in it.

Work packages’ interdependencies are studied on a task-by-task basis, both at the submission stage and at launch of the project, and the project timeframe for transformational adaptation for the six demonstrators is presented in the Pert chart in Figure 2.

Figure 2 TransformAr Pert Chart

3.2 Roles and responsibilities

The following actors will be engaged in the process for the review of deliverables.

Work Package and Deliverable (Task) Leaders: They allocate tasks and coordinate the work of the contributors, and are responsible to consolidate the inputs of all contributors into the draft deliverable to be submitted for review and publication.

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC will be involved in the entire review process, meaning that the PC must review both the draft version submitted for review by the respective Deliverable (Task) Leader and the revised version submitted after addressing the comments raised by the internal reviewers. The PC will be reviewing all deliverables. The PC is responsible for the final submission of the deliverable to the European Commission.

Technical Manager (TM): The TM will be involved in the entire review process, meaning that the TM must review both the draft version submitted for review by the respective Deliverable Leader and the revised

version submitted after addressing the comments raised by the internal reviewers. The TM will be reviewing all deliverables.

Administrative and Financial Manager (AFM): The AFM will be involved in the entire review process, and in particular the final stages of the review process to ensure that the deliverable complies with the template and quality required, and that the deliverable is ready to be uploaded. The AFM is involved in the final submission of the deliverable to the European Commission.

Project management team: One member of the project management team will be in charge of the final editing of the deliverable before the official submission to the Participant Portal. This is a final technical check that the deliverable complies with the template and that the deliverable is ready to be uploaded, ensuring that the text is free of spelling/grammar/syntactic/semantic errors, as well as of comments, and highlighted text. Other aspects (page numbering and table of contents, figures, tables, etc.) will be also checked.

3.3 Deliverable review process

The deliverable review process of TransformAr follows a schedule that begins five weeks before the official deadline of the deliverable deadline. The full review process is presented in Table 5 below, beginning with a verification of the beginning of the review process by the TransformAr project management team with the Work Package Leader and Deliverable (Task) Leader of the relevant deliverable deadline.

Table 5 Deliverable review process

When	Who (initiator)	What	Recipient
5 weeks before submission deadline	Project management team (PC, TM or AFM)	Verifies deliverable deadline and start of review process with relevant partner(s)	Work Package Leader and Task Leaders of relevant deliverable
4 weeks before the official submission deadline	Deliverable (Task) Leader	Submits the first draft of the deliverable	Work Package Leader and Project Coordinator
3 weeks before official submission deadline	Project Management Team and Work Package Leader	Return deliverable with comments and feedback	Deliverable (Task) Leader
2 weeks before official submission deadline	Deliverable (Task) Leader	Submit reviewed deliverable based on comments and feedback from Project Management Team and Work Package Leader	Project Management Team and Work Package Leader
1 week before official submission deadline	Project Management Team and Work Package Leader	Final review, editing and verification of compliance with quality standards	Deliverable (Task) Leader for final verification
Submission to European Commission's Participant Portal by the TransformAr Project Management Team by deliverable deadline			

3.4 Quality criteria for deliverables

The quality of the deliverables will be assessed against specific quality criteria in order to ensure uniformity and consistency in the review process of all deliverables and to facilitate the reviewers' clear understanding of and compliance with the process. The criteria, along with the aspects to be investigated are outlined in Table 6 below:

Table 6 Quality criteria for deliverables

Quality Criteria	Description
Consistency	The content of the deliverable is consistent with the description of the task in the TransformAr Work Plan.
Compliance	All aspects of the deliverable, as described in the Grant Agreement are fully addressed.
Objective consistency	The objectives of the deliverable are in line with project objectives
Scope consistency	The content of the deliverable is in line with the scope of the deliverable and relevant to its target audience.
Accuracy	The content of the deliverable is scientifically sound and supported by relevant and well-sourced references.
Clarity	The language of the text is clear (proper sentence structure is used); The text is in consistent English (whether UK or US); The text is unambiguous; The terminology, including acronyms, is explained; There are no spelling errors; Any potentially sensitive information is appropriately worded
Technical consistency	The deliverable is submitted using the relevant templates.

Figure 3 TransformAr Gantt Chart

The timing of TransformAr deliverable deadlines are presented in the Gantt chart shown in Figure 3. An overview of TransformAr deadlines in order of Work Packages and relevant dates has been prepared by the TransformAr project management team is available for all consortium members in the Microsoft Teams WP8 channel to keep track of upcoming deadlines.

3.5 Quality assurance of other output

The other scientific and policy-related outputs of the project, i.e. project commentaries, briefings and working documents, will also be reviewed before they are published, mainly for compliance with the respective templates and quality criteria. As there are no deadlines and no formal submission for these materials, the process only includes one step, delivery of the draft document by the dissemination leader, based on the inputs of the authors, and a technical check by the management team from UA and Euroquality.

3.6 Technical quality assurance

TransformAr template have to be used for all output created within the project (available for all project partners in the Microsoft Teams Platform in the Work Package 7 file). The templates provide general structures to be followed for the following documents:

Deliverables

- Table of contents
- Executive summary
- Sections – including introduction and conclusions
- Subsections
- Annex

Agenda

- TransformAr XXXX MEETING - AGENDA
- XXXX meeting, MONTH XX, 20XX
- Location: XXXX
- Link: XXX
- Contact person:
- Meeting time
- Start; end of session; subject; presenter; duration

Meeting minutes

- MINUTES OF <MEETING NAME>
 - Date:
 - Place:
 - Author(s):
 - WP/Task/Subtask:
 - Version
 - List of Participants
 - List of Apologies
 - Main action points
 - Minutes
 - Time-Title
-

3.7 TransformAr naming convention

All documents for the project should adhere to the following naming convention:

TransformAr-[WP]-[Deliverable]-[title]-[ver]-[day]-[month]-[year].[ext]

4.0 Project Reporting

4.1 Internal communication

The Microsoft Teams working space is a working platform accessible only to consortium members, where they can share the project working documents and deliverables, and have calls, chats and web conferences. It is a Microsoft tool, integrating all the Microsoft usual office features, authorising and facilitating online collaboration on Word, Excel or PowerPoint documents.

Some areas of the working space may have a restricted access to specific members of the consortium if needed. The general organisation of the project Teams is presented beneath in Figure 4.

Seamless follow-up of the project progress is supported by a general mailing list as well as specific groups within the Teams working space. The general e-mail account has been set up to facilitate the communication with the coordination team:

transformar@euroquality-project.eu

The full mailing list is accessible on the Teams working space for all partners and presents the contact details of all members of partner organisations involved in TransformAr.

Figure 4 Figure on the organisation of folders

4.2 External communication

TransformAr will actively carry out communication activities to reach out to a large community of stakeholders, including change-agents, representatives of key community systems, environmental organisations, public and private scientists, policymakers and the general public. A dual approach will be implemented: at demonstrator scale (local and regional) for implementing the TransformAr activities; and at European scale, for ensuring TransformAr exploitation and wide replicability of TransformAr solutions. The communication activities of the project will involve the use of mass media to share relevant information of the project to the wider public. The editorial coverage in the press, or on the web, reaches large audiences and the consortium partners will make use of regional, national and European media

together. The main objectives in the Communication Plan (Figure 5) are to (i) raise awareness and interests of stakeholders and end-users (demo scale), (ii) identify, engage, and mobilise the stakeholders (demo scale), (iii) transfer knowledge by generating communication and dissemination materials, and participation in social networks, conferences, and events (EU scale), and (iv) ensure a broad applicability of results, by generating a multiplication effect via training events (EU scale). The project communication strategy will include an exhaustive section aimed at following up and monitoring its implementation to detect potential low impact at an early stage and implement relevant corrective actions. To facilitate the monitoring and assessment of the impact, quantitative objectives will be established, and a monitoring plan carried out requiring periodical partners' reports on results of communication actions.

Figure 5 Communication Plan

The communication tools of TransformAr are adapted to reach a wide audience and public. In the following Table 7, the channels that will be used in the project are presented, with the public targeted described.

Table 7 TransformAr communication tools

Communication Channels	Description		
Website	Water Europe will design and develop a dedicated TransformAr website to communicate the project and disseminate its findings (www.transformar.eu). It will enable effective communication between the project and external stakeholders, the press and the wider EU public. It will also provide the consortium members with a dedicated information exchange space to ease the smooth work completion.		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.30)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Visits per year</i>	<2.000	2.000 – 5.000	>5.000
Social media	News will be distributed on relevant social media channels such as Twitter (https://mobile.twitter.com/transformareu) and LinkedIn (https://www.linkedin.com/company/transformargreendeal). It will offer a tool to report unfolding developments during the course of the project. News will contain amongst others: 1) Project press releases; 2) Announcements of progress; 3) Reports on conferences and meetings, 4) News of milestone achievements, 5) Information about forthcoming events; 6) News on research and developments in process related issues from all over the world.		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.31)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Followers</i>	<500	500 – 1.000	>1.000

Communication materials	Water Europe will design the communication materials during the project lifetime to be used by partners when necessary. These materials will be centralised in a branding guideline document to guarantee an effective and consistent branding of the project; and updated regularly to be adapted to the different messages to be communicated. Therefore, project partners will be responsible for local adaptation including translation to different European languages and printing.		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.32)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Brochures distributed</i>	<1.000	1.000 – 3.000	>3.000
Digital and media press work	Digital and physical campaigns will be set-up for the promotion of the TransformAr activities and website. Translations will be made by the demonstrator partners.		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.33)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Articles published</i>	<20	20 – 40	>40
Open field days	These on-site events and communication sessions will be organised for each territory involved in the project to promote solutions identified in the project and explain transformational adaptation of the territories. The technical details will be presented in a vulgarised way to be understandable by the public that will be the main target of these sessions. Questions and answers times will be also planned to ensure the good comprehension and a better support to the project		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.34)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Number of people attending</i>	<80	80 – 120	>120
Collaboration with other projects and networking	TransformAr will forge communication with other European or national projects related to adaptation and in particular those funded under the same call. This will promote synergies with other projects and networks (especially those identified in WP7), as well as the establishment of cluster participation in events and publications, promoting the dissemination potential of TransformAr website by sharing news and links. These synergies will facilitate project partners to disseminate the project's results to other H2020 or Horizon Europe projects (particularly those under the Mission Adaptation).		
<i>Key indicators</i>	<i>Poor impact</i>	<i>Good impact (KPI.35)</i>	<i>Excellent impact</i>
<i>Collaborations</i>	<3	3 – 6	>6

4.3 Cost monitoring

For each month of the project, a detailed timesheet template (in Project Management WP8 channel, in the D8.2 folder) is proposed to monitor the time per person, and per Work Package, per week. Partners of the project can also use their own internal templates if they have some. The first table at the top of each month summarises the total effort of the partner for the month considered. The created timesheets document also allows partners to follow and report their other costs. It includes Subcontracting, Travel costs, Equipment costs and Other goods and services. The total is gathered and presented in the last sheet of the document.

4.4 Official reporting

The Project Coordinator will submit to the EC the technical and financial reports set out in the Grant Agreement.

The TransformAr project is divided into 3 Reporting Periods (RPs):

1. RP1 from M1 to M18;
2. RP2 from M19 to M36;
3. and RP3 from M37 to M48.

Payments are linked to the reporting periods, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Reporting periods and linked payments

Thus, 3 **Periodic Reports** (PR) will have to be submitted by the Project Coordinator within 60 days after the end of each reporting period. PRs are composed of a (i) **Periodic Technical Report** part and of a (ii) **Periodic Financial Report**. In addition to the PRs, for the last reporting period, the coordinator must submit the Final Report within 60 days following the end of the last reporting period

The financial reporting should be done in real time by all partners with the timesheets template (see 3.1 Timesheets for personnel costs) that also includes the sheets for cost monitoring (cf. 3.2 Cost monitoring).

For the official Financial Reporting, EQY has created one template with the same sections as the online financial reporting tool to encourage partners to begin their financial reporting in advance.

For efficient management, EQY will implement Control Reports (CR). Each partner will report, 6 months before each Periodic Report (M12, M30), all publications, dissemination, staff effort per Work Package, travels and equipment costs, etc. EQY will then review partners' financial reports to ensure consistency.

Financial reporting in a nutshell

1. Each TransformAr partner should complete in real time the timesheet template (either the one proposed by EQY on the Teams repository, or its own template)
2. These monthly timesheets should be kept internally by partners in case of audit and to have the information ready for Periodic Reports
3. At Month 12 and at Month 30, EQY will gather timesheets (for personnel and other costs monitoring), information on publications, dissemination activities etc. to prepare Control Reports
4. These Control Reports will in turn prepare the official Financial Reporting part of the Periodic Reports (first one due at Month 18 and second one due at Month 36).

5.0 Risk management

5.1 Risk analysis and mitigation measures

A first assessment of implementation and management risks was made by TransformAr partners and is presented in Table 8. Each risk is assessed according to its likelihood (L, from 1 to 3) and its severity (S, from 1 to 3). The combination of likelihood and severity will generate a classification of risks.

Table 8 Preliminary risk assessment

Risk description	WP	L	S
Delay in implementation due to Covid-19	all	3	2
This will be carefully monitored by the project team from the start of the project to manage problems at an early stage and a buffer-period of 6 months has been foreseen. Also, project meetings can be done remotely, as all partners have gathered significant expertise during the last year.			
Lack of financial resources	all	1	3
Solvency of project partners has been assessed, ensuring their financial resources during the project execution. Almost all partners have already participated in national or EU projects, having a wide experience and history, which reduces this risk. However, the corrective measures would be distribution to the remaining partners of the activity not fulfilled and/or to subcontract to a 3rd party.			
Withdraw from consortium: One of the partners withdraws from the consortium.	all	1	3
The core partners are well established organisations. Many of the partners have already worked together successfully in the past. In case of withdrawal of a non-core partner, its tasks and responsibilities could be reallocated to another partner with a minor impact to the project results. Otherwise, they would find within their large contact network the best partner for assuming the role lost.			
Project delayed: A deliverable or milestone is delayed.	all	3	2
Extra effort will be generated in project management to confine the effect of the delay. Strict project management and monitoring techniques will be used to ensure that critical paths are not influenced by the missed deadline.			
Lack of interest from demonstrator participants	1	2	3
Tailored communication activities will be reinforced at local scale to engage stakeholders on a long-term basis; incentives may be considered.			
Lack of data to achieve the project goals	3	2	3
Additional support from territories in data collection and in the digital transformation of existing data will be provided.			
Poor communication flow between partners	8	2	3
T8.2 has been specifically made to limit this risk. If the tools provided by EQY and the monthly conference are not enough, new measures will be decided to ensure that internal communication works.			
Lack of comprehension of guidance provided on ethical and data management issues	8	1	2
Introduce a discussion forum at the second Consortium meeting that subsequently continues on-line.			
Complex or out-of-project data processing	3	2	2
To assess the most efficient plan to carry out these particular data processing needs.			
Poor articulation between biophysical models for climate risks and impacts	2	1	2

CMCC, together with ACTERRA, E3M, PIK and NCSRD, have been closely collaborating during the setting up process to avoid and mitigate such risks. During TransformAr, continuous exchanges will take place between these partners, to avoid any silo-effect.

Poor knowledge transfer between Methodological developers and Technical support partners	all	1	2
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The methodology has been elaborated during the setting up of the project in collaboration with all partners. Both methodological developers and technical support have foreseen appropriate PMs for the transfer in their budget.

5.2 Conflict resolution

If necessary, the project coordinator will organise a conflict resolution meeting within 30 days following the reception of a written request transmitted by any of the TransformAr partners. Attempts at arbitration will be performed in increasing order of authority:

- Within the team of each work package under the management of the Work Package Leader
- Within the Executive Committee under the management of the project coordinator

Any risks or discrepancy within work packages shall be first resolved on the work package level by means of dialogue and mutual concession. In case of failure, decisions from higher levels will be requested, and suggestions for potential solutions and answers will be prepared.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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